

Porous Bleed Boundary Conditions for Shock-Induced Boundary Layer Separation Control

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ABSTRACT

Porous bleed systems are widely used to mitigate the shock-induced boundary layer separation, e.g., in supersonic air intakes. However, the complex geometry makes simulations expensive and motivates the application of suitable models.

In this paper, seven porous bleed models are implemented as boundary conditions in the in-house compressible RANS solver **elsA**. The models are compared to a three-dimensional reference simulation, including the porous bleed geometry. Different options are introduced to compare the model outcomes on different levels.

None of the models is found to be suitable for the application in the shock-boundary layer interaction control. No model can accurately estimate the mass flow rate for sub- and supersonic conditions. Moreover, the approach based on a uniform suction leads to an overestimation of the porous bleed performance. Thus, the shock-induced boundary layer separation is suppressed.

1. INTRODUCTION

The porous bleed is a proven technology to mitigate the flow separation caused by shock-boundary layer interactions and stabilize the shock system. Generally, it is placed below the shock foot, e.g., in supersonic air intakes. Typical bleed regions consist of plates with hundreds of small holes covering a cavity (see Fig. 1). The removal of air from the cavity generates a lower pressure than in the external flow, which enables the removal of the low-momentum air in the boundary layer of the external flow. Thus, the boundary layer profile upstream of the shock becomes fuller and more resistant to adverse pressure gradients. Besides, the air inside the separated

region downstream of the shock is sucked away.

While the working principle of porous bleeds is quite simple, predicting the extracted mass flow rate and the effect on the flow field is still challenging. Thus, the design of porous bleed regions in industrial cases is problematic as simulations including all bleed holes, which are typically in the size of the displacement thickness of the boundary layer, are too expensive. In the past, multiple porous bleed models have been introduced. These models can be directly applied as a boundary condition at the wall, and no mesh refinement is required.

In this investigation, existing porous bleed models are presented. The models are implemented as a boundary condition in a RANS solver. A reference simulation of a shock-boundary layer interaction including the porous bleed is performed as a benchmark to evaluate the bleed models in different steps. First, the bleed models are analytically assessed based on the benchmark data. Hereafter, simulations with the models are conducted to com-

Figure 1: Schematic of a porous bleed

pare the performance of the models. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first comprehensive comparison of several bleed models.

2. POROUS BLEED MODELS

2.1 General

In the following, several models are presented in the order of their publication. All equations have been transcribed in the notation shown in Fig. 1. Important here is the distinction between hole properties (subscript h), which annotate the flow quantities in a hole, and bleed values (subscript bl), computed for the whole bleed area A_{bl} . The bleed area

$$A_{bl} = \underbrace{\phi A}_{\text{Boundary condition}} = \underbrace{\sum A_h}_{\text{Reality}} \quad (1)$$

is the corrected area of the patch A using the (local) porosity ϕ in the simulation with a bleed boundary condition. This correction is required as the blowing and suction are applied on all patch cells and not locally distributed. In reality, the bleed area describes the sum of all hole areas. For the presentation of the bleed models, only the final equations are shown. For more details regarding the models and their derivations, see the corresponding reference.

2.2 Abrahamson and Brower (1988)

The bleed boundary condition introduced by Abrahamson and Brower [1] is an analytical approach to compute the transpiration flow velocity across the plate by using the isentropic mass flow rate. The transpiration velocity is expressed as

$$v_{bl} = \frac{c_b p_{pl} \phi}{\rho_w T_w} \sqrt{\left(\frac{p_w}{p_{pl}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} \left[\left(\frac{p_w}{p_{pl}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right] \frac{2\gamma}{R_s(\gamma-1)}} \quad (2)$$

for unchoked holes or as

$$v_{bl} = \frac{c_b p_{pl} \phi}{\rho_w T_w} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{R_s} \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2} \right)^{\frac{-(\gamma+1)}{2(\gamma-1)}}} \quad (3)$$

for choked flow with a pressure ratio $p_{pl}/p_w < 0.528$. The variable c_b is an empirically derived constant which was found for a good agreement with the experiments of Hingst and Tanji [2]. Those experiments have been carried out for free-stream Mach numbers $M = 2.47$ and $M = 1.98$ and an oblique shock-boundary layer interaction. The hole diameter was chosen to be $D = 3.17$ mm, the porosity level $\phi = 34.8$ %.

2.3 Poll et al. (1992)

The bleed model of Poll et al. [3] is also an analytical model to compute the transpiration flow without considering external flow. Here, the flow through the individual holes is regarded to be laminar. Moreover, the effects of compressibility are neglected. The relation between pressure drop and mass flow rate is expressed as

$$\frac{\Delta p d^2}{\rho v^2} \left(\frac{d}{t} \right)^2 = 40.7 \frac{\dot{m}_{bl}}{\mu t} \left(1 + 0.05 \frac{\dot{m}_{bl}}{\mu t} \right) \quad (4)$$

with the pressure drop

$$\Delta p = p_w - p_{pl}. \quad (5)$$

2.4 Harloff and Smith (1996)

The model of Harloff and Smith [4] is an approach to model the flow through a single hole or slot by using the conservation of mass, momentum, and energy as well as empirical relations. Here, only the equations for a 90-degree hole are presented. The idea is to model the discharge coefficient of the hole for different geometries and depending on the local flow conditions. Therefore, discharge coefficient correctors for the pressure effect ΔC_D^P , the effect of flow separation ΔC_D^S , and the length-to-diameter effect $\Delta C_D^{L/D}$ are added to the initial discharge coefficient.

$$C_D = C_{D,i} + \Delta C_D^P + \Delta C_D^S + \Delta C_D^{L/D} \quad (6)$$

The discharge coefficient itself depends on the Mach number on the boundary layer edge M_e . Without external flow, the incompressible discharge coefficient $C_{D,i} = 0.82$ is taken into account and corrected according to the length-to-diameter ratio. For Mach numbers $M_e < 0.6$, the discharge coefficient is based on the incompressible discharge coefficient and the discharge coefficient of Bragg [5], which in turn is a function of the pressure ratio and the incompressible discharge coefficient $C_D^B = CD(C_{D,i}, p_{pl}/p_w)$. For higher Mach numbers, only the discharge coefficient of Bragg [5] is applied.

$$C_D = C_{D,i} + \Delta C_D^{L/D} \quad \text{if } M_e = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$C_D = \frac{C_{D,i} + C_D^B}{2} \quad \text{if } 0 < M_e < 0.6 \quad (8)$$

$$C_D = C_D^B \quad \text{if } M_e \geq 0.6 \quad (9)$$

The correction of the pressure effect is only taken into account for high Mach numbers $M_e > 0.84$ and pressure ratios $p_{pl}/p_w > 0.5$ when the presence of internal flow separation is assumed.

$$\Delta C_D^P = -0.46 \left(\frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} - 0.5 \right) \quad \text{if } \begin{cases} M_e > 0.84 \\ \frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} > 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta C_D^P = 0 \quad \text{else} \quad (11)$$

Moreover, depending on the Mach number M_e , flow separation based on convection effects is considered. The higher the Mach number, the lower the corrector ΔC_D^S is.

$$\Delta C_D^S = -0.1M_e \quad \text{if } M_e \leq 0.6 \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta C_D^S = -0.06 - 0.4(M_e - 0.6) \quad \text{if } 0.6 < M_e \leq 1.0 \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta C_D^S = -0.22 - 0.217(M_e - 1.0) \quad \text{if } 1.0 < M_e \leq 1.6 \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta C_D^S = -0.35 \quad \text{if } M_e > 1.6 \quad (15)$$

The last considered effect is the length-to-diameter ratio effect. For long holes, the friction losses are assumed to be higher. Thus, the discharge coefficient is increased for lower ratios.

$$\Delta C_D^{L/D} = 0.08 \quad \text{if } L/D < 3 \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta C_D^{L/D} = 0 \quad \text{if } L/D \geq 3 \quad (17)$$

For the computation of the bleed mass flow rate \dot{m}_{bl} , the sonic mass flow rate \dot{m}_{sonic} needs to be determined first. Therefore, the sonic area

$$A_{sonic} = \phi A \frac{216}{125} M_h (1 + 0.2M_h^2)^{-3} \quad (18)$$

is computed with the hole exit Mach number

$$M_h = \sqrt{5 \left(\frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \right)^{-2/7} - 5}. \quad (19)$$

By knowing the sonic area, the sonic mass flow rate can be calculated as follows:

$$\dot{m}_{sonic,w} = A_{sonic} p_w \left(\frac{\gamma}{RT_w} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2} \right)^{\frac{-\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}}. \quad (20)$$

Finally, the bleed mass flow rate can be computed.

$$\dot{m}_{bl} = C_D \dot{m}_{sonic,w} \quad (21)$$

The model of Harloff and Smith [4] is validated on different experimental datasets [6, 7].

2.5 Doerffer and Bohning (2000)

Doerffer and Bohning [8] provide a porous bleed boundary condition based on the experimental data of the EUROSHOCK project [9]. The tested perforated plates have hole diameters from 0.085 mm to 0.325 mm and porosity levels from 2.27 % to 24.9 %. It should be noted that the porosity stated by Doerffer and Bohning [8] is an aerodynamic (measured) porosity. Moreover, the validation of the model with an external flow is based on only one plate with a hole diameter of $D = 0.185$ mm and a porosity level of $\phi = 5.05$ % or $\phi = 5.30$ % depending on the

direction of installation. They found a relation between the pressure difference over the plate and the effective Mach number in the holes. Suction and blowing are distinguished because the suction mass flow rate is reduced for increasing external flow velocities.

In the case of suction, the following relation is applied:

$$\frac{p_w - p_{pl}}{p_w} = M_h^{0.555} \left[\left(\frac{1}{1.2} \right)^{0.555} + 25 \left(\frac{|\tau_w|}{\frac{\rho_h u_h^2}{2}} M_h \right)^{\frac{1}{1.52}} \right]. \quad (22)$$

Here, the wall shear stress τ_w quantifies the external flow velocity. Its value is normalized by the dynamic pressure of the flow in the hole. In contrast, there is no influence of the external flow on the observed blowing mass flow rate. Hence, the pressure difference is only a function of the effective Mach number, as shown in Eq. 23.

$$\frac{p_{pl} - p_w}{p_{pl}} = M_h^{0.555} \left[\left(\frac{1}{1.2} \right)^{0.555} \right] \quad (23)$$

Finally, with the knowledge about the hole Mach number, the mass flow rate can be computed

$$\dot{m}_{bl} = \phi A \rho_h \frac{M_h \sqrt{\gamma R T_0}}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M_h^2}} \quad (24)$$

with T_0 being T_w for suction and T_{pl} for blowing.

2.6 Slater (2012)

The bleed boundary condition of Slater [10] is an empirical model based on the supersonic experiments of Willis et al. [7] for the C1 plate with a hole diameter of $D = 6.35$ mm and a porosity level of $\phi = 19.1$ %. The sonic flow coefficient

$$Q_{sonic,w} = \frac{\dot{m}_{bl}}{\dot{m}_{sonic,w}} \quad (25)$$

is scaled with respect to wall conditions using the bleed mass flow rate \dot{m}_{bl} and the sonic mass flow rate for wall conditions

$$\dot{m}_{sonic,w} = p_w \phi A \left(\frac{\gamma}{RT_w} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2} \right)^{\frac{-\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}}. \quad (26)$$

The scaling is applied to eliminate the Mach number at the boundary layer edge from the equations. Otherwise, the extraction at the boundary layer edge would be required, which is complex and almost impossible for separated or distorted flows. The sonic flow coefficient for wall conditions is the efficiency of the bleed device. It can be modeled using the quadratic curve fit

$$Q_{sonic,w} = -0.57 \left(\frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \right)^2 + 0.6 \quad (27)$$

as a function of the pressure ratio of plenum pressure and external wall pressure.

2.7 Choe et al. (2020)

The model of Choe et al. [11] is a variation of the boundary condition of Slater [10]. Slater [10] assumes a wall pressure equal to the pressure on the boundary layer edge. By contrast, Choe et al. [11] take the effect of the local flow expansion caused by the porous bleed into account. Already Baurle and Norris [13] found an underestimation of the bleed boundary condition of Slater [10] caused by the missing consideration of the local flow expansion. The new scaling of Choe et al. [11] leads to the new quadratic curve fit

$$Q_{sonic,w} = 0.6756 - 0.8086 \left(\frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \right)^2 + 0.1846 \frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \quad \text{if } \frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \geq 0.2634 \quad (28)$$

$$Q_{sonic,w} = 0.6681 \quad \text{if } \frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} < 0.2634 \quad (29)$$

by using the same validation data [7].

2.8 Grzelak et al. (2021)

Grzelak et al. [12] introduced a bleed model based on a numerical database of single-hole simulations without external flow. The simulations are experimentally validated by measuring the mass flow rate for three different porous plates up to choking conditions. The principle is modeling the flow efficiency η , which describes the flow losses. Using the flow efficiency, the Mach number at the hole outlet can be computed

$$M_h = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma-1} \left[\left(1 + \eta \left(\frac{p_w}{p_{pl}} - 1 \right) \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right]} \quad (30)$$

as a function of the pressure ratio from total hole inlet pressure, which is equal to the wall pressure p_w for no external flow, to the static hole outlet pressure, here described by the plenum pressure p_{pl} .

By knowing the hole exit Mach number, the mass flow

rate of the boundary condition can be computed as

$$\dot{m}_{bl} = \phi A [p_{pl} + \eta(p_w + p_{pl})] \sqrt{\frac{\gamma M_h^2}{RT_w \left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M_h^2 \right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{\gamma-1}}}} \quad (31)$$

The flow efficiency is expressed as

$$\eta = 0.429\phi - 0.01803 \frac{L}{D} + 0.64472, \quad (32)$$

which is a function of the porosity level ϕ and the length-to-diameter ratio L/D . The validation range goes from 4 % to 10 % for the porosity level and 1.5 to 8 for the length-to-diameter ratio.

2.9 Scope of application

For the control of shock-boundary layer interactions, various aspects need to be considered in the modeling of the porous bleed to guarantee a correct operation. For strong shock-boundary layer interactions, both sub- and supersonic flows must be controlled upstream and downstream of the shock. Moreover, the intense pressure gradient and shock instabilities can lead to static pressure in the plenum being higher than the static pressure in the supersonic flow. Thus, blowing occurs and needs to be considered in the modeling. In contrast, the plenum pressure is very low if the shock is located close to the end of the porous bleed. So, the pressure ratio over the perforated plate is very high in the subsonic region and may be smaller than the critical pressure ratio. Consequently, the holes are choked.

Tab. 1 gives an overview of the range of validation for the different models. The models of Poll et al. [3] and Grzelak et al. [12] are validated without external flow. So, there is no differentiation between blowing and suction (o). The model of Doerffer and Bohning [8] is the only model with a separate relation for blowing. In summary, it can be stated that no bleed model covers all possible situations which may appear in the presence of a shock-boundary layer interaction.

Model	External flow		Choked holes	Blowing
	Subsonic	Supersonic		
Abrahamson and Brower	-	✓	✓	-
Poll et al.	-	-	-	o
Harloff and Smith	✓	✓	✓	-
Doerffer and Bohning	✓	-	-	✓
Slater	-	✓	✓	-
Choe et al.	-	✓	✓	-
Grzelak et al.	-	-	✓	o

Table 1: Validated scope of application for the different models

Figure 2: Schematic of the investigated problem

3. PHYSICAL PROBLEM

The modeled problem corresponds to the test section in the S8Ch wind tunnel at the ONERA in Meudon (see Fig. 2). It derives from a previous test set-up devoted to transitional shock-boundary layer interaction [14]. The chosen scenario is an interaction of a shock with a turbulent boundary layer. The nozzle is formed to create a free-stream Mach number of $M = 1.6$ with a boundary layer thickness of $\delta \approx 5$ mm, a displacement thickness of $\delta_1 \approx 0.55$ mm, and a Reynolds number of $Re_{\delta_2} \approx 5300$ based on the momentum thickness. A shock generator with an angle of attack of $\alpha = 10^\circ$ is used to generate an irregular shock reflection at the wall. The shock generator's leading-edge is located at the nozzle exit, with its distance to the floor being $y = 84.5$ mm. Thus, a normal shock is present in the vicinity of the wall.

Control of the shock-boundary layer separation is applied by a porous bleed. It is located with an offset of 40 mm to the nozzle exit and has a length of 40 mm. With the aim to achieve a ratio of $D/\delta_1 \approx 1$ typically for technical applications [4], the hole diameter is chosen to be 0.5 mm. The porosity level of the perforated plate is $\phi = 14.51\%$, and the length-to-diameter ratio is $L/D = 1$.

The inlet works under atmospheric conditions. Furthermore, an expansion fan exists caused by the finite length of the shock generator. The first expansion waves reflect on the wall slightly downstream of the porous bleed region.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Three-dimensional reference simulation

A three-dimensional RANS simulation serves as a benchmark to evaluate the existing models. The compressible Navier-Stokes equations are solved using the in-house finite-volume solver **elsA**. The turbulence is modeled us-

ing the Spalart-Allmaras model with quadratic constitutive relation [15]. The mesh, generated by the in-house mesh-generator **Cassiopee**, is fully parametric and structured, which allows a variation of the geometry of the perforated plate. It consists of a total of 6.1 M. cells.

Figure 3: Mesh near the holes for the three-dimensional reference simulation

The porous bleed is modeled out of two half rows of holes in span-wise and 32 holes in stream-wise direction. Symmetry planes on the hole centerlines in span-wise direction are applied to reduce the computational costs. A visualization of the mesh topology near the holes is shown in Fig. 3. The bleed plenum has the size of the bleed region, and its exit is shaped like a nozzle to fix the mass flow rate under choked conditions. The choked area is sized with regard to the bleed area. Therefore, the throat area

$$TR = \frac{A_{pl,ex}}{A_{bl}} \quad (33)$$

is introduced to define the working regime of the bleed for different configurations.

4.2 Simulation with bleed boundary condition

For the simulation with the porous bleed boundary condition, the solver and the turbulence model are equal to the reference simulation. Again, a structured mesh generated with the in-house mesh-generator **Cassiopee** is used. In this simulation, the porous bleed is substituted by a boundary condition. Thus, neither the holes nor the plenum is included in the mesh. Thus, the mesh is simplified and consists only of one cell in the span-wise direction. The porous bleed boundary condition is implemented using the porous bleed models presented in Sec. 2. The spatial resolution in stream-wise direction is with $dx = 0.5$ mm similar to the displacement thickness. Hence, the porous bleed area is discretized in 80 cells. Higher resolutions have only minor effects on the extracted mass flow rate. All simplifications reduce the total mesh size to only 0.1 M. cells.

The computation of the bleed boundary condition is performed in **Python** and carried out regularly after a predefined number of iterations. Therefore, several flow variables are extracted from the latest flow solution. The in-house CFD solver **elsA** enables access to all flow variables on the cell center after each iteration. Moreover, all variables can be extracted at the faces of the boundary condition.

Figure 4: Extraction locations in the mesh

Fig. 4 gives an overview of the extraction locations. The circles illustrate the cell centers and the squares the interface on the boundary condition. All positions where variables are extracted are marked in red. The red vertical line symbolizes the extraction of the Mach number on the boundary edge required for the bleed model of Harloff and Smith [4]. The solver **elsA** offers multiple options to define the boundary layer edge to extract variables. Here, the *BLX-like* method implemented by Bégou [16] is used. The static wall pressure and temperature applied for the bleed models are extracted on the interface of the boundary condition (■). The wall shear stress, required for the model of Doerffer and Bohning [8], is calculated using the flow properties in the first cell center (●) and the wall

distance dy :

$$\tau_w = \mu \frac{du}{dy}. \quad (34)$$

Equation 34 can be applied since the wall is defined as a viscous wall, and the dimensionless wall distance is $y^+ \approx 1$. The tangential velocity is assumed to be zero at the wall since the porosity level is relatively low.

The blowing and suction are applied to the first row of cells using source terms. The following source terms are adapted from Baurle and Norris [13] and added to the compressible Navier-Stokes equations.

$$\text{Continuity:} \quad \frac{q_{bl} A_c}{V_c} \quad (35)$$

$$\text{Momentum:} \quad \frac{q_{bl}^2 A_c}{\rho V_c} + \frac{(p_{bl} - p_w) A_c}{V_c} \quad (36)$$

$$\text{Energy:} \quad \frac{q_{bl} c_p T_l A_c}{V_c} \quad (37)$$

The physical values applied in the source terms are directly extracted from the first cell centers (●). All bleed model outputs are converted to a surface bleed mass flux q_{bl} . The local mass flow rate is computed using the surface mass flux and the projected patch area of the cell A_c . All source terms are normalized using the local cell volume V_c .

Three options to set the working regime of the porous bleed for the computation of the bleed models are possible:

1. Fixed plenum pressure p_{pl}
2. Fixed mass flow rate \dot{m}_{bl}
3. Fixed throat ratio TR .

The definition of the plenum pressure is the classical way to define the working regime used by all existing models. To determine a constant mass flow rate, the plenum pressure is iteratively adjusted until the desired mass flow rate is achieved. If the throat area is defined, the mass flow rates through the perforated plate and the choked mass flow through the plenum exit are computed. The plenum exit mass flow rate is a function of the plenum pressure. Here again, the plenum pressure is iteratively adjusted until the mass balance is achieved. The definition of a throat ratio enables the comparison between the three-dimensional simulation, where the mass flow rate is also fixed by a choked nozzle, and the simulations with the bleed boundary conditions.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Reference case

For porous bleed, normal blowing is generally unwanted as it increases the size of the boundary layer and makes it

Figure 5: Mach contour for the reference simulation; dotted line illustrates the sonic line

less resistant to adverse pressure gradients. Thus, the reference case is computed for the throat ratio $TR = 0.7$. In this case, the porous bleed works in a full suction mode, which means that the plenum pressure is low enough to guarantee no blowing into the boundary layer.

The flow field is visualized in Fig. 5. In the supersonic area upstream of the shock, a thinning of the boundary layer can be observed. Consequently, an expansion fan is created at the beginning of the plate. The upstream bleed aims to remove the low-momentum air near the wall to make the boundary layer less delicate to separate when it interacts with the impinging shock. The zoom to the supersonic region in Fig. 5 depicts the flow field in this area. The holes are unchoked, the flow separation inside the holes is large, and thus, the vena contracta area is significantly smaller than the hole area.

Downstream of the shock, the bleed mass flow rates are higher, resulting from the higher pressure difference from the external flow to the plenum. In this case, the holes are choked as seen in the zoom on the right in Fig 5. Despite the high bleed mass flow rate, a thickening of the boundary layer is visible.

Fig. 6 shows the curves for the static wall pressure (Fig. 6a), the wall shear stress in streamwise direction (Fig. 6b), and the mass flux through the wall (Fig. 6c). The values are extracted on the solid surfaces around the holes. The incident shock is clearly seen in all curves located at $x = 65$ mm. Upstream of the shock, the static wall pressure is almost constant. Downstream of the shock, the wall pressure increases.

The effect of the porous bleed can be seen by observing the wall shear stress in Fig. 6b. In the supersonic region, where the boundary layer is thinned, the wall shear stress slightly increases, which corresponds to a fuller boundary layer profile. Further downstream, the adverse

Figure 6: Extracted curves from the reference simulation

pressure gradient of the shock wave decreases the flow velocity near the wall significantly, and the wall shear stress becomes almost zero. Then, the wall shear stress increases again, which is the effect of removing the low-momentum flow near the wall.

The influence of the static wall pressure is clearly visible on the bleed mass flux (see Fig. 6c). The mass flux in the supersonic region is relatively low since the static wall pressure is also low. The pressure rise caused by the shock leads to a higher pressure difference between the external flow and bleed plenum. This results in a higher mass flux through the wall.

Throat ratio TR	Plenum pressure p_{pl}	Mass flow rate \dot{m}_{bl}
0.7	18 324 Pa	10.198 g/s

Table 2: Porous bleed properties

The characteristics of the working regime of the porous bleed are summarized in Tab. 2. The static plenum pressure is only slightly lower than the external static wall pressure in the supersonic region. All these values are applied to the following simulations with the bleed boundary conditions.

5.2 Bleed boundary conditions

5.2.1 Analytical comparison

The evaluation of the existing bleed models is performed in multiple steps. As a first step, the outcome of the models is compared analytically without running a simulation. Therefore, the extracted values shown in Fig. 6 are applied to compute the bleed mass flux as predicted by the model. Using the data of existing experiments and simulations is the typical approach in defining a bleed model. Therefore, a good fit of models and simulation is expected.

It must be noted that the definition of the boundary layer edge is challenging in the case of a shock-boundary layer interaction. For this reason, the model of Harloff and Smith [4] is not included in the analytical comparison. It requires the definition of the Mach number on the boundary layer. The therefore needed extractor can not be applied in the simulation with holes as the mesh is not aligned in the wall-normal direction.

Fig. 7 shows the different models compared with the reference simulation for this analytical comparison. All model outcomes are converted to the bleed mass flux, which is used to compute the source terms. Moreover,

Figure 7: Bleed mass flux computed by the bleed model compared to the reference case

the relative model error

$$\epsilon = \frac{q_{bl,mod} - q_{bl,ref}}{q_{bl,ref}} \quad (38)$$

is calculated to show the difference between model bleed mass flux $q_{bl,mod}$, and reference bleed mass flux $q_{bl,ref}$. Here, the relative error ϵ is shown only in the range $\pm 50\%$ to focus on the best fitting models.

At first glance, a significant mismatch between the models and the reference mass flux in the subsonic area becomes apparent. However, only the model of Abrahamson and Brower [1] misestimates the bleed mass flux by more than 50%. In contrast, two models (Poll et al. [3] and Grzelak et al. [12]) overestimate the mass flux in the supersonic flow regime by more than 50% what is expected as both models are only validated without external flow.

Important to see is the difference in the accuracy for sub- and supersonic conditions. No model has an equal error for both conditions. The model of Doerffer and Bohning [8] is the only model which is able to predict the mass flux at almost every position within a relative error of $\pm 25\%$. Upstream of the shock, the mass flux is overestimated while downstream of the shock it is too low. The model of Slater [10], which is purely validated on experimental supersonic data, fits the best in the supersonic region but underestimates the bleed mass flux downstream of the shock.

5.2.2 Applied bleed models in RANS solver

For a higher-level comparison, simulations with the implemented bleed boundary conditions are performed. With this, all the implemented bleed options presented in Sec. 4.2 are used. Fig. 8 shows the results of the simulations with the different bleed boundary conditions. For the bleed options, the values of Tab. 2 are applied. In Fig. 8a, the static plenum pressure has been defined. The differences between reference simulation and the simulations with the bleed models are clearly visible. All bleed models seem to overestimate the bleed mass flux in the supersonic regime. For subsonic conditions, the outcome of the models spread a lot. Remarkable is the strong influence of the bleed mass flux in the subsonic region on the position of the shock. The higher the mass flux in this area, the further downstream the shock foot is which can be seen by the steep increase of the mass flux. Also, the transition from supersonic to subsonic conditions seems more abrupt and less smeared than in the reference simulation.

Fig. 8b shows the results for the simulations where the bleed mass flow rate has been fixed. Interestingly, by setting the mass flow rate, all models are able to predict the shock position correctly. Also, the scattering of the model outcome for subsonic conditions is smaller. In general, all models have a lower difference in the bleed mass flux

downstream of the shock. In contrast, the bleed models differ more significantly in the area upstream of the

Figure 8: Bleed mass flux computed for different plenum options

shock.

The last option to compute the bleed models is the definition of the throat ratio shown in Fig. 8c. Since neither the plenum pressure nor the mass flow rate are fixed, a balance needs to be established. Consequently, the outcomes of the models lie between those with fixed plenum pressure or bleed mass flow rate.

The observation of Fig. 8 shows the lack in modeling a porous bleed by a boundary condition in the presence of a normal shock. The model of Harloff and Smith [4] has the best agreement with the reference simulation. Please note that the model of Abrahamson and Brower [1] can not be considered for the options of a fixed bleed mass flow rate and throat ratio as the model computes a negative plenum pressure for such high mass flow rates.

A comparison of all models can be found in Tab. 3. Here, the total bleed mass flow rate, respectively the static plenum pressure computed by the model are compared for the different plenum options and the analytical comparison. Surprisingly, the model of Choe et al. [11] has the lowest deviation from the reference simulation. The reason is the balance between the overestimated mass flux in the supersonic region and the underestimated mass flux in the subsonic region. Thus, the model performs with regard to the total values well, although the local error is high.

It is also important to see the difference between the analytical comparison and the simulation with the fixed plenum pressure. It reveals that the bleed models behave in a different manner than expected. Actually, the outcome should be similar to the analytical comparison since the constraints are identical. However, as the bleed models actively influence the flow, the wall properties vary, and hence their input. Consequently, a correction of the models, or the approach, should be required to mimic the real behavior of the porous bleed.

A significant difference between analytical comparison and simulation is observed for the model of Doerffer and Bohning [8] as shown in Fig. 9. The first plot (Fig. 9a) shows the curves for the static wall pressure. For all three plenum options, the incident shock position is reasonably predicted. However, the pressure increases with a higher

Model	Analytical	Const. p_{pl}	Const. \dot{m}_{bl}	Const. TR	
	\dot{m}_{bl}	\dot{m}_{bl}	p_{pl}	\dot{m}_{bl}	p_{pl}
Abrahamson and Brower	-64.20 %	-56.54 %	-	-	-
Poll et al.	+54.86 %	+32.28 %	+13.53 %	+12.41 %	+8.47 %
Harloff and Smith	-	+9.18 %	+8.58 %	+6.34 %	+3.02 %
Doerffer and Bohning	-2.48 %	-26.37 %	-65.62 %	-16.92 %	-19.23 %
Slater	-28.75 %	-21.24 %	-25.08 %	-10.08 %	-12.61 %
Choe et al.	-11.01 %	-8.06 %	-7.66 %	-2.47 %	-5.29 %
Grzelak et al.	+49.50 %	+26.02 %	+10.93 %	+10.20 %	+6.69 %

Table 3: Deviation of the bleed models compared to the reference simulation

gradient. The curves are less smeared and look more similar to the inviscid theory. Moreover, a discrepancy in the pressure upstream of the shock can be noted. For the simulation with the fixed mass flow rate, the wall pressure is lower. This is a consequence of a stronger expansion fan at the beginning of the porous bleed area caused by the higher mass flux in this region (see Fig. 9c).

The evolution of the wall shear stress is shown in Fig. 9b. At the first sight, a strong overestimation of the wall shear stress is observed. If the bleed mass flow rate is fixed, the wall shear stress in the supersonic region is approximately four times higher than in the reference case. Consequently, the momentum close to the wall is very high, and the boundary layer very thin and resistant against adverse pressure gradients. Quite contrary to the reference case, there is no drop in the wall shear stress caused by the shock but an increase.

Downstream of the shock, the wall shear stress is even higher and reaches around ten times the amount of the reference case if the bleed mass flow rate is fixed. The overestimation of the wall shear stress can be explained by the constant suction in all cells. While the air removal occurs in reality only locally through the holes, the same amount of mass flow is here distributed uniformly to the whole patch. This increases the efficiency of the porous bleed as we have no shocks and expansion fans caused by the flow into the holes. As a result, the boundary layer becomes way thinner and fuller. This effect is a consequence of the general approach and can be noted for all bleed models.

Moreover, the overperformance of the porous bleed boundary conditions strongly affects the shock-boundary layer interaction. As most of the boundary layer is removed, the interaction is strongly mitigated as almost no more boundary layer exists. Consequently, the solution becomes closer to an inviscid shock solution. On the one hand, this explains the intense pressure rise, and on the other hand, the non-existence of a drop in the wall shear stress. In other words, a continuous porous bleed boundary condition is not suited for the application below a shock foot. The efficiency of the boundary condition is way higher than in reality. Thus, a shock-induced boundary layer separation will consistently be underestimated in size or never occur, no matter which bleed model is used.

Besides, it must be noted that the criterion $y^+ \approx 1$ can not be guaranteed for such high increases of the wall shear stress. Consequently, the application of Eq. 34 tends to underestimate the wall shear stress.

The observation of the bleed mass fluxes (Fig. 9c) identifies a significant problem of the bleed models. While the model fits quite accurately the reference simulation in the analytical comparison, the error of the implemented model is inacceptably high, as shown in Fig. 9d. The main reason for the mismatch of the model of Doerffer

and Bohning [8] is the consideration of the shear stress in Eq. 22. They found a degradation in the bleed performance for high wall shear stresses. As stated before, the wall shear stress is overestimated, and consequently, the bleed mass flux is reduced. Surprisingly, Baurle and Norris [13] found an overestimated bleed mass flow rate for

Figure 9: Evaluation of the model of Doerffer and Bohning [8] for different approaches

Figure 10: Mach contour for the simulation with bleed boundary condition (black patch) and reference simulation

the Doerffer and Bohning [8] model in their comparison. In our view, they defined the wall shear stress corresponding to its value upstream of the porous bleed as a constant and did not extract the wall shear stress locally.

The high error for the simulations with the fixed bleed mass flow rate and throat ratio (see Fig. 9d) can be explained based on the primary trend of the model. The model of Doerffer and Bohning [8] tends to overestimate the bleed mass flux for supersonic flows while underestimating the bleed mass flux for subsonic flows. As stated in the last paragraph, the total mass flow rate is minimized because of the unrealistic wall shear stresses. If the overall mass flow rate is fixed, the mass flux must be increased, and consequently, the overestimation in the supersonic region is enforced. Also, for the case with the defined throat ratio, the mass flow rate and, as a result, the mass flux are increased but less intense. Thus, the error is lower.

Fig. 10 highlights all the differences stated before between the reference simulation and the simulation with boundary condition. The Doerffer and Bohning [8] model overestimates the mass flux in the supersonic region which results in a slightly thinner boundary layer. More significant are the differences downstream of the shock. The boundary layer is thicker in the simulation with the bleed boundary condition caused by the underestimated mass flux. This can be noted by observing the sonic line

(dotted line), which is in the reference simulation closer to the wall. Nevertheless, the Mach number in the vicinity of the wall seems to have a similar or even higher value than in the reference simulation despite the lower mass flux in this region.

6. CONCLUSION & OUTLOOK

In this paper, we have evaluated seven porous bleed models based on a three-dimensional reference simulation. The results confirm that none of these models is suited for the application below a shock foot. Even though the bleed mass flow rate and the plenum pressure are comparable to the reference simulation for some models, the local deviation is too high for an application. Generally, bleed models lack of accuracy on both sub- and supersonic conditions.

An important limitation of bleed boundary conditions is the approach to define a uniform blowing and suction. As a consequence, the porous bleed overperforms, which results in an unrealistic overestimation of the wall shear stress. Thus, the flow becomes highly resistant against adverse pressure gradients induced by shocks, and the flow does not tend to separate as in reality. Moreover, all bleed models are introduced based on experimental or numerical data, where blowing and suction were performed only locally in the holes.

Future work will focus on defining a local porosity for each cell. In our view, this approach will improve the performance of porous bleed boundary conditions as it is closer to the reality where suction and blowing occur only locally through the holes.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Abrahamson and D. Brower, "An empirical boundary condition for numerical simulation of porous plate bleed flows," in *26th Aerosp. Sci. Meet.* Reno, Nevada: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, jan 1988. <http://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/6.1988-306>
- [2] W. Hingst and F. Tanji, "Experimental investigation of a two-dimensional shock-turbulent boundary layer interaction with bleed," in *21st Aerosp. Sci. Meet.* Reno, Nevada: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, jan 1983. <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/6.1983-135>

- [3] D. I. A. Poll, M. Danks, and B. E. Humphreys, "Aerodynamic Performance of Laser Drilled Sheets," Univ. of Manchester. Aeronautical Engineering Group., Tech. Rep., 1992.
- [4] G. J. Harloff and G. E. Smith, "Supersonic-inlet boundary-layer bleed flow," *AIAA J.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 778–785, apr 1996. <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/3.13140>
- [5] S. L. Bragg, "Effect of Compressibility on the Discharge Coefficient of Orifices and Convergent Nozzles," *J. Mech. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 35–44, mar 1960. http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1243/JMES_JOUR_1960_002_007_02
- [6] J. Syberg and J. L. Koncsek, "Bleed System Design Technology for Supersonic Inlets," *J. Aircr.*, vol. 10, no. 7, pp. 407–413, jul 1973. <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/3.60241>
- [7] B. Willis, D. Davis, and W. R. Hingst, "Flow coefficient behavior for boundary layer bleed holes and slots," in *33rd Aerosp. Sci. Meet. Exhib.* Reno, Nevada: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, jan 1995. <http://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/6.1995-31>
- [8] P. P. Doerffer and R. Bohning, "Modelling of perforated plate aerodynamics performance," *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 4, no. 8, pp. 525–534, nov 2000. <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1270963800010634>
- [9] E. Stanewsky, J. Délery, J. Fulker, and P. Matteis, *Drag Reduction by Shock and Boundary Layer Control*, E. Stanewsky, J. Délery, J. Fulker, and P. Matteis, Eds., Berlin, Heidelberg, 2002, vol. 53, no. 9. <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-540-45856-2>
- [10] J. W. Slater, "Improvements in Modeling 90-degree Bleed Holes for Supersonic Inlets," *J. Propuls. Power*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 773–781, jul 2012. <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/1.B34333>
- [11] Y. Choe, C. Kim, and K. Kim, "Effects of Optimized Bleed System on Supersonic Inlet Performance and Buzz," *J. Propuls. Power*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 211–222, mar 2020. <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/1.B37474>
- [12] J. Grzelak, P. Doerffer, and T. Lewandowski, "The efficiency of transpiration flow through perforated plate," *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 110, mar 2021. <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1270963821000067>
- [13] R. A. Baurle and A. T. Norris, "A Source-Term Based Boundary Layer Bleed/Effusion Model for Passive Shock Control," *58th JAN-NAF Propuls. Meet.*, 2011. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20110011133>
- [14] J.-P. Dussauge, R. Bur, T. Davidson, H. Babinsky, M. Bernardini, S. Pirozzoli, P. Dupont, S. Pionniau, L. Larchevêque, R. Giepmans, F. Schrijer, B. van Oudheusden, P. Polivanov, A. Sidorenko, D. Szubert, M. Braza, I. Asproulias, N. Simiriotis, J.-B. Tô, Y. Hoarau, A. Sansica, and N. Sandham, "WP-1 Reference Cases of Laminar and Turbulent Interactions," in *Notes Numer. Fluid Mech. Multidiscip. Des.*, P. Doerffer, P. Flaszynski, J.-P. Dussauge, H. Babinsky, P. Grothe, A. Petersen, and F. Billard, Eds. Cham.: Springer International Publishing, 2021, vol. 144, no. Transition Location Effect on Shock Wave Boundary Layer Interaction: Experimental and Numerical Findings from the TFAST Project, pp. 25–127. http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-030-47461-4_2
- [15] P. Spalart, "Strategies for turbulence modelling and simulations," *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 252–263, jun 2000. <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0142727X00000072>
- [16] G. Bégou, "Prévision de la transition laminaire-turbulent dans le code elsA par la méthode des paraboles," Ph.D. dissertation, Université de Toulouse, 2018. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/tel-01878439>